

Research Article

Effect of Processing Methods on the Nutritional Value of Tropical Almond
(*Terminalia catappa* L.) Kernel Meal for Aqua Feed

¹Falaye, A. E. and ²Elezuo, K. O.

¹Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, University of Ibadan,
Ibadan, Nigeria. Email: ae.falaye@gmail.ui.edu.ng

²Department of Fisheries Technology, Federal College of Fisheries and Marine
Technology, Victoria Island, Lagos, Nigeria.

Abstract

Five processing methods, boiling, roasting, soaking in water, mechanical extraction and solvent extraction were used to investigate the effect of processing methods on nutrient composition of the tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa*) kernel meal. The raw almond kernel meal (RWAM) (control) and the five differently processed meals were analyzed for their proximate, mineral and anti-nutrients composition using standard methods. Data obtained were subjected to ANOVA at $p= 0.05$. The results showed that Solvent Extracted Almond Kernel Meal (SEAM) had significantly higher ($p<0.05$) crude protein content (35.38%), followed by Mechanical Extracted Almond Kernel Meal (MEAM, 30.64%) while Boiled Almond Kernel Meal (BOAM) had the lowest value (24.07%). Crude fat significantly ($p<0.05$) varied from 1.86% (SEAM) to 30.27% in RWAM. Crude fibre ranged from 3.33% to 3.79%. SEAM had the highest ash value (4.87%) while Soaked Almond Kernel Meal (SOAM) had the lowest value (2.78%). Nitrogen free extract ranged between 28.16% in RWAM and 46.15% in MEAM. Sodium ranged between 0.035% in MEAM and 0.091% in SEAM. ROAM had the highest potassium and calcium values 0.367% and 0.29% respectively, while SEAM and RWAM had the lowest values (0.235 % and 0.20%) respectively. Phosphorus ranged between 0.21% in RWAM and 0.50% in ROAM. There were significant differences

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

($p < 0.05$) among the treatments' mean values for the minerals. Oxalate, phytate, tannin and trypsin inhibitor were significantly high ($p < 0.05$) in RWAM (0.051%, 0.092%, 0.065% and 22.47 TIU/mg respectively) while they were significantly low ($p < 0.05$) in ROAM (0.013%, 0.035%, 0.026% and 0.01 TIU/mg respectively). All the processing methods reduced the anti-nutritional factors present in almond kernel. However, roasting, solvent extraction and mechanical extraction seem to be superior processing methods for almond kernel and the meals made using these methods have high potential of being utilized as protein concentrates in aqua feed.

Keywords: protein concentrates, anti-nutrients, nutrient composition, fish feedstuff, boiling, roasting, extraction

Received: 12/05/18

Accepted: 29/07/18

Introduction

The fish feed industry is still very dependent on fish meal and fish oil from the industrial fishing operations. Fish meal is a major protein source in aquaculture feeds. However, its supply is not growing worldwide (Tacon, 1994) and it depends entirely on landings from the capture fisheries. Moreover, the price of fish meal is often high (Falaye *et al.*, 2014).

There is an increasing demand for more insight on the potential of alternative/low-cost protein sources in aqua feeds (New and Wijkstrom, 2002). Considerable research has been conducted to evaluate the suitability of various feed ingredients as an alternative protein source for the conventional protein concentrates in aqua feed especially fishmeal and soya bean meal (Nwanna, 2003; Solomon and Sadiku, 2005, Fagbenro *et al.*, 2010; Elezuo *et al.*, 2011; Falaye *et al.*, 2016). According to Rumsey (1993) increased use of plant protein feedstuff in fish diet will reduce feed cost and assist in reducing dependence on fishmeal as fish protein feed stuff. But due to the rising cost of some conventional plant protein source like soybean arising from competition between man and livestock industry, the search for an alternative to fishmeal has been on and many workers have utilized various unconventional protein supplements from plants.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Several nuts and kernels exist that could be explored for nutritional potentials for aqua feeds. One of such kernels is tropical almond kernel. Tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa* Linnaeus) is a widely growing plant in West Africa (Burkill, 1988). The tree is more of an ornamental plant used as sunshade and for land scaping than food; but

Continental J. Biological Sciences

provides fruits that are consumed by man especially children (Elezuo *et al.*, 2011). It is readily and locally available. Global production is around 1.7 million tons annually (Molody, 2008). Nigeria produces about 0.1 million tons annually (Annongu *et al.*, 2006). Tropical almond has a kernel yield estimated at about 5kg per tree per year and 10kg per tree per year for selected genetic stock grown on high quality sites (Traditional tree, 2006). The plant fruits twice in a year and it is estimated that only about 20% of the fruit is consumed, the remaining 80% being wasted (Burkill, 1988). However, the fruit is a good source of nutrients, the kernel contains about 51% oil, 23.1% crude protein and 9.3% crude fibre (Burkill, 1988). Elezuo *et al.* (2011) reported that almond kernel contains 29.65% crude protein while Ezeokonkwo and Dodson (2004) reported that it contains 25.81% crude protein. This makes the kernel meal a potential alternative protein source in aqua feed. However, it is well known that plants generally contain anti-nutrients most of which are naturally-occurring chemicals (Igile, 1996). Some of these chemicals are known as “secondary metabolites” and they have been shown to be highly biologically active (Zenk, 1991). They include saponins, tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, trypsin (protease) inhibitors, oxalates, phytates, hemagglutinins (lectins), cyanogenic glycosides, cardiac glycosides, mimosine, gossypol etcetera. Some of these plant chemicals have been shown to be deleterious to health or evidently advantageous to human and animal health if consumed in appropriate amounts (Kersten *et al.*, 1991; Sugano *et al.*, 1993). Most of these secondary metabolites elicit very harmful biological responses, while some are widely applied in nutrition and as pharmacologically-active agents (Oakenfull and Sidhu, 1989; Soetan, 2008). However, most of the toxic and anti-nutrient effects of these compounds in plants could be removed or reduced by several processing methods such as soaking in water, germination, boiling, autoclaving, fermentation, genetic manipulation and other processing methods (Soetan, 2008). Processing of various feedstuffs is very crucial as adequate processing techniques improve digestibility of feedstuffs, removes anti nutritional factors and destroy unwanted contaminant that could inhibit utilization of nutrient. According to Balogun (2013), before the adoption of a given feedstuff in aqua feed, preliminary tests for its proximate composition, nutritional value and health implications of its consumption are essential and permit credible recommendations with regards to its quality and use.

**This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria**

However, information on the effect of processing methods on the nutrient and anti-nutritional factors composition of the almond kernel is scarce. This study therefore examined the effect of processing methods on the nutritional value of tropical almond kernel meal with the aim of propagating it as a low cost unconventional fish feedstuff.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To investigate the effect of different processing methods on the proximate and mineral composition of tropical almond kernel meal.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of different processing methods in reducing the anti-nutritional factors present in tropical almond kernel meal.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection and preparation

Almond fruits were manually picked from almond trees at Nnamdi Azikiwe Hall, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. They were sundried for four days. The dried fruits were placed on a hard platform, cracked with a hammer and the kernels were manually brought out from their shells.

Processing of Almond kernel into meals

The raw almond kernels were sundried for three days. The dried kernels were measured into six places, each measuring one kilogramme. A portion was milled with a Thomas Wiley milling machine (Model K 925) and designated as raw almond kernel meal (RWAM). Another portion was boiled in water at 100° C and atmospheric pressure for 30 minutes at a proportion of 1:1.5 (kernel to water) w/v ratio (Ijeh and Elezuo, 2008; Orisasona, 2014). The boiled kernels were drained, sundried for three days, milled with a Thomas Wiley milling machine (Model K 925) and designated as boiled almond kernel meal (BOAM). Another portion was soaked in water at room temperature for 24 hours at a proportion of 1:2 (kernel/water) w/v ratio (Ijeh and Elezuo, 2008). The water was drained and changed at 12-hour interval. After soaking, the kernels were drained, sundried for three days, milled and designated as a soaked almond kernel meal (SOAM). A fourth portion was put in a stainless steel pan, placed over a Stuart Scientific, electric cooker (model SH 1) and roasted at 80° C for 4 hours until the kernel coat became dark brown (Sotolu, 2008; Adesina, 2014) and emitted a characteristic aroma similar to that of roasted melon. The roasted kernels were milled with a Thomas Wiley milling machine (Model K 925) and designated as roasted almond kernel meal

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

(ROAM). Another portion was ground with a Thomas Wiley milling machine (Model K 925) and de-oiled in a soxhlet apparatus containing petroleum spirit (boiling point range 60°-80° Celcius) for 6-12 hrs. It was put in stainless steel tray, air-dried for 4 days and sun-dried for one day for complete removal of residual solvent (Bello et al., 2012; Falaye et al., 2016) and designated as solvent extracted almond kernel meal (SEAM). The last portion was milled and loaded into the receptacle of a locally made mechanical screw press and pressed for 24 hours. Oil was collected in a compartment at the base of the screw press, removed through a tap and stored in a bottle. The resultant cake was manually broken into fine particles and designated as mechanically extracted almond kernel meal (MEAM). The raw and differently processed almond kernel meals were stored in air-tight labeled plastic containers and kept in a cool dry place.

Analytical Procedure

Samples of the raw and differently processed almond kernel meals were subjected to proximate analysis in accordance with Standard methods described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (A.O.A.C), 2005. All analysis was done in triplicates.

Crude protein was determined by the routine semi-micro Kjeldahl procedure. The percentage crude protein was calculated by multiplying the total nitrogen by a factor of 6.25. %Nitrogen (N) = Titre value x atomic mass of Nitrogen x Normality of HCl used x 4.

Crude fat was determined by subjecting the samples to a continuous extraction with petroleum ether using soxhlet apparatus as described by A.O.A.C. (2005)

Ash content was determined by subjecting the oven dried samples with known weight to ignition in a muffle furnace set at 550°C and left for about four hours after which the samples were cooled in desiccators and weighed. The percentage ash was calculated from the formula:

$$\text{Ash content} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{Original weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Crude fibre was determined after the samples were defatted and ashed in a Gallenkamp muffle furnace at 600°C for 5 hours. The percentage crude fibre content was calculated as follows:

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Crude fibre content (%) = $W_1 - W_2 / W_1 \times 100$

Where W_1 = Initial weight of sample (g)

W_2 = final weight of sample (g)

The moisture content was determined by oven drying known weight of the samples at 100°C to dry to a constant weight for 24 hours. The samples were cooled in desiccators for ten minutes before weighing. The moisture content was calculated using the formula:

% Moisture = $(W_1 - W_3) \times 100 / (W_1 - W_0)$

Where, W_0 = weight of empty crucible, W_1 = weight of crucible plus sample (before oven drying), W_3 = weight of crucible plus oven-dried sample (AOAC, 2005).

Nitrogen-free extract was determined by subtracting the sum of (% Moisture + % Crude protein + % crude fat + % crude fibre + % Ash) from 100.

Samples of the raw and differently processed almond kernel meal were analyzed for mineral content. The mineral elements were determined using the standard method of AOAC (2005). This was done by subjecting the samples to flame emission spectrophotometry using Jenway digital flame photometer (P7P model) after being digested with 2M HCl. They were later filtered using the filter corresponding to each mineral element. The concentration of each element was calculated using the formula:

% mineral = $\text{Metre reading} \times \text{Slope} \times \text{dilution factor} / 10000$

The anti-nutritional factor tannin was determined according to the method of Swain (1979), oxalate was determined following the method of Henry (1993). Trypsin inhibitor was determined following the Casein digestion method of Kakade *et al.* (1974). Phytate was determined as described by Maga (1983).

Statistical analysis

Data resulting from the experiment were subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software. Determination of significant mean differences among individual means was done at $p=0.05$ using Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1955).

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Results and Discussion

The proximate compositions of raw and differently processed Tropical Almond kernel meals are presented in Table 1 while Table 2 shows the mineral composition of raw and differently processed Tropical Almond kernel meals. Results of anti-nutritional factors composition of raw and differently processed Tropical Almond kernel meals are presented in Table 3.

Boiled Almond Kernel meal (BOAM) yielded the lowest crude protein value of 24.07% while Solvent Extracted Almond kernel meal (SEAM) yielded the highest crude protein value. There was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the mean crude protein values. Fat content of RWAM was highest (30.27%) followed by ROAM (29.86%) and least in SEAM (1.86%). Crude fibre content had a narrow range of 3.33% to 3.79%. Value for ash was highest in SEAM (4.87%) while SOAM had the least value (2.78%). Moisture content was lowest in ROAM (4.85%) while BOAM had the highest value (13.65%).

Table 1: Proximate composition of raw and differently processed tropical almond kernel meals (Means \pm SEM)

Parameters (%)	Processing methods (treatments)					
	BOAM	SOAM	ROAM	MEAM	SEAM	RWAM
Crude protein	24.07 \pm 0.08 ^a	28.16 \pm 0.06 ^b	28.58 \pm 0.11 ^c	30.64 \pm 0.07 ^d	35.38 \pm 0.06 ^e	28.73 \pm 0.05 ^c
Crude fibre	3.58 \pm 0.01 ^c	3.65 \pm 0.01 ^d	3.33 \pm 0.01 ^a	3.49 \pm 0.02 ^b	3.79 \pm 0.01 ^e	3.75 \pm 0.01 ^e
Crude fat	20.86 \pm 0.01 ^d	18.38 \pm 0.02 ^c	29.86 \pm 0.02 ^e	7.28 \pm 0.02 ^b	1.86 \pm 0.02 ^a	30.27 \pm 0.02 ^e
Ash	3.31 \pm 0.02 ^b	2.78 \pm 0.01 ^a	3.95 \pm 0.01 ^d	3.76 \pm 0.01 ^c	4.87 \pm 0.01 ^f	4.28 \pm 0.02 ^e
Moisture	13.65 \pm 0.01 ^f	13.18 \pm 0.02 ^e	4.85 \pm 0.02 ^a	8.52 \pm 0.02 ^c	8.86 \pm 0.0	5.81 \pm 0.01 ^b
Nitrogen-free extract	34.78 \pm 0.10 ^d	34.01 \pm 0.09 ^c	29.18 \pm 0.11 ^b	46.15 \pm 0.07 ^f	45.24 \pm 0.06 ^e	28.16 \pm 0.41 ^a
*Gross energy	4.33 \pm 0.02 ^{bc}	4.30 \pm 0.01 ^{bc}	4.43 \pm 0.02 ^{ab}	3.32 \pm 0.02 ^d	3.32 \pm 0.02 ^d	4.87 \pm 0.02 ^a

Mean values in each row with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$).

*Unit of Gross Energy not % but Kcal/g

Legend: BOAM = boiled almond kernel meal; SOAM = soaked almond kernel meal; ROAM = roasted almond kernel meal; MEAM = mechanically extracted almond kernel meal; SEAM= solvent extracted almond kernel meal; RWAM = Raw almond kernel meal

Table 2: Mineral composition of raw and differently processed Tropical Almond kernel meals. Means \pm SEM

Minerals (%)	Processing methods (treatments)					
	BOAM	SOAM	ROAM	MEAM	SEAM	RWAM
Sodium	0.052 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.064 \pm 0.00 ^d	0.045 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.035 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.091 \pm 0.00 ^f	0.078 \pm 0.00 ^e
Potassium	0.256 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.255 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.367 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.260 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.235 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.261 \pm 0.00 ^b
Calcium	0.26 \pm 0.01 ^{cd}	0.23 \pm 0.01 ^{bc}	0.29 \pm 0.02 ^d	0.27 \pm 0.01 ^{cd}	0.22 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.20 \pm 0.01 ^a
Magnesium	0.252 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.272 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.269 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.264 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.329 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.299 \pm 0.00 ^b
Phosphorus	0.33 \pm 0.01 ^c	0.22 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.50 \pm 0.01 ^e	0.42 \pm 0.01 ^d	0.27 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.21 \pm 0.01 ^a
Iron	0.031 \pm 0.00 ^{ab}	0.024 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.035 \pm 0.00 ^{ab}	0.046 \pm 0.00 ^{bc}	0.027 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.059 \pm 0.00 ^c

Mean values in each row with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$).

Legend: BOAM =boiled almond kernel meal; SOAM = soaked almond kernel meal; ROAM = roasted almond kernel meal; MEAM = mechanically extracted almond kernel meal; SEAM= solvent extracted almond kernel meal; RWAM = Raw almond kernel meal

Table 3: Anti-nutritional factors composition of raw and differently processed Tropical Almond kernel meals (Means \pm SEM)

Anti-nutritional factors (%)	Processing methods (treatments)					
	BOAM	SOAM	ROAM	MEAM	SEAM	ROAM
Oxalate	0.026 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.029 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.013 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.021 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.040 \pm 0.00 ^d	0.051 \pm 0.00 ^e
Phytate	0.052 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.065 \pm 0.00 ^d	0.035 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.043 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.074 \pm 0.00 ^e	0.092 \pm 0.00 ^f
Tannin	0.036 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.050 \pm 0.00 ^d	0.026 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.032 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.052 \pm 0.00 ^d	0.065 \pm 0.00 ^e
*Trypsin inhibitor (TIU/mg)	5.66 \pm 0.02 ^c	7.17 \pm 0.02 ^d	0.01 \pm 0.00 ^a	3.09 \pm 0.01 ^b	13.90 \pm 0.02 ^e	22.47 \pm 0.03 ^f

Mean values in each row with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$).

Legend: BOAM =boiled almond kernel meal; SOAM = soaked almond kernel meal; ROAM = roasted almond kernel meal; MEAM = mechanically extracted almond kernel meal; SEAM= solvent extracted almond kernel meal; RWAM = raw almond kernel meal

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

Sodium values ranged between 0.035% and 0.091 % while potassium ranged between 0.235% and 0.367%. Calcium was highest in ROAM (0.29%) while it was least in RWAM (0.20%). Phosphorus was highest in ROAM (0.50%) followed by MEAM (0.42%) and least in RWAM (0.21%). Iron ranged between 0.024 and 0.059%. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the treatments' mineral values.

Oxalate was highest (0.051%) in RWAM and least (0.13%) in ROAM (Table 3). Phytate was highest (0.092%) in RWAM (control) and least in ROAM (0.035%). Tannin ranged between 0.026% and 0.065% while Trypsin inhibitor ranged between 0.01 to 22.47TIU/mg. There were significant differences in the values of the anti-nutritional factors amongst the treatments.

Processing of the tropical almond kernel meal using different methods produced variation in their chemical composition. This observation agrees with the findings of Oyelese (1994), Omitoyin (1995) and Olukunle (1996). They had earlier observed that processing of the test feedstuffs (cassava peels, poultry by-products and sesame seed respectively) produced variations in their chemical composition.

The results of the present study showed that solvent extracted almond kernel meal (SEAM) had the highest crude protein content (35.38%), followed by mechanically-extracted almond kernel meal (MEAM) (30.64%) while boiled almond kernel meal (BOAM) had the least value of 24.07%. The high crude protein content of SEAM could be attributed to the concentration of the remaining compounds (nutrients) after extraction of the oil component. This is consistent with the report of Adesina (2014) who attributed high protein content of solvent extracted sunflower seed meal to the concentration of all inorganic solvent-soluble components after the separation of the organic solvent-soluble portion of the meal. The lower crude protein content of boiled almond kernel meal could be attributed to leaching and/ or breakdown of protein during boiling. This observation agrees with the reports of Giami and Ikpimi (1992) which reported reduction in the protein content of sunflower seed meal processed by boiling. It is also consistent with the report of Iyayi and Egharevba, (1998) who reported a reduction in crude protein content of boiled *Mucuna utilis* seeds compared to the raw seeds.

Raw almond kernel meal had the highest fat content followed by roasted almond kernel meal while solvent extracted tropical almond kernel meal had the lowest crude fat content. The crude fat content of raw and differently processed almond kernel meals in

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

the present study (1.86 to 30.27%) is lower than the value of 36.0% reported by Olapade and Kargbo (2012) for raw almond kernel meal.

Crude fibre contents of raw and differently processed tropical almond kernel meal samples had a narrow range of 3.33% to 3.79% and were lower than those of Falaye *et al.*, (2014) for lima bean (4.77-6.87) and Adesina (2014) (14.19%-23.94%) for processed sunflower seed meals. Ash content was highest (4.87%) and the least (2.78%) in the solvent extracted and soaked almond kernel meals respectively. This is similar to those obtained by Falaye *et al.* (2014) (3.65-4.36%) for processed lima bean. The moisture content was least in roasted almond kernel meal (4.85%) and highest in boiled almond kernel meal (13.65%). The low moisture content of the roasted almond kernel meal could be attributed to the direct removal of moisture by roasting.

Nitrogen free-extract (NFE) content of the differently processed tropical almond kernel meals ranged from 28.16 to 46.15% with the least and highest values recorded for raw and mechanically extracted almond kernel meals respectively. The high nitrogen-free extract content of the differently processed tropical almond kernel meals is an indication that they can also serve as an energy source in aqua-feed. Solvent-extracted tropical almond kernel meal had the least gross energy value while raw tropical almond kernel meal had the highest value followed by roasted almond kernel meal. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the gross energy content of the raw and differently processed meals. The high gross energy content of raw and roasted almond kernel meals could be attributed to the high crude fat content of these two meals compared to the other meals.

All the processing methods resulted in an increase in the calcium and phosphorus content of tropical almond kernel meal. This is similar to the report of Sotolu (2008) who observed increase in the calcium content of roasted and soaked *Leucaena* seed compared to the raw (sundried) one. Solvent extraction resulted in an increase in Magnesium and sodium content of tropical almond kernel (compared to the raw meal) while the other processing methods slightly reduced these minerals. This is in agreement with the report of Falaye *et al.* (2014) which observed reduction in Magnesium content of Lima bean seed processed by toasting, soaking, boiling and autoclaving. The high magnesium and sodium content of SEAM could be attributed to the concentration of the remaining nutrients (including some minerals) after extraction of the oil component. Roasting significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased potassium content of the tropical almond kernel meal while the other processing methods caused a slight

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

reduction in potassium values. All the processing methods caused a reduction in the iron content of the tropical almond kernel meal. Generally, the differently processed almond kernel meals had a good mineral profile.

Apart from trypsin inhibitor, the levels of anti-nutritional factors in tropical almond kernel meals in this study were generally low. Oxalate was in the range of 0.013 to 0.026%, phytate 0.035 to 0.092% and tannin 0.026 to 0.065%. This is relatively low compared to that of Adesina (2014) with the ranges 0.11 to 0.18% for oxalate, 0.11 to 0.16% for phytate and 0.21 to 0.45% for tannin for differently processed sunflower seed meals. It is also relatively low compared to that of Falaye et al., (2014) with ranges 0.62 to 1.09% for oxalate, 0.73 to 1.04% for phytate and 0.044 to 0.09% for tannin for differently processed lima bean meals.

All the processing methods employed in this study reduced the levels of anti-nutritional factors, namely oxalate, phytate, tannin and trypsin inhibitor present in raw tropical almond kernel meal. Tannin content reduced from 0.065% for the raw kernel meal to 0.052% for the solvent extracted kernel meal, 0.050 for the soaked kernel meal, 0.036% for the boiled kernel meal, 0.032% for the mechanically extracted kernel meal and 0.026 for the roasted kernel meal. The reduction in the level of tannin resulting from the various processing methods employed in this study is in line with the recommended methods for removal of condensed tannins from seeds which includes dehulling, autoclaving, heat treatment (boiling and roasting) and fermentation (Griffiths, 1991).

Oxalate has been reported to reduce the physiological value of calcium in seeds (Johnson *et al.*, 1979). For this study, oxalate significantly reduced from 0.051% in the raw kernel meal to 0.040 for solvent extracted kernel meal, 0.0290% for the soaked kernel meal, 0.0257% for the boiled kernel meal, 0.021% for mechanically-extracted kernel meal and 0.013% for the roasted kernel meal.

Phytic acid occurs naturally throughout the plant kingdom and is present in considerable quantities within many of the major legume and oil seeds. Spinelli *et al.* (1983) reported that about 62-73% and 46-73% of the total phosphorus within cereal grains and legume seeds are in the form of organically bound phytin phosphorus respectively. The major part of the phosphorus contained within phytic acid is largely unavailable to monogastric animals due to the absence of the enzyme phytase within the digestive tract of monogastric animals. Phytic acid acts as a strong chelator, forming protein and mineral-phytic acid complexes; the net result being reduced protein and

**This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria**

mineral bioavailability (Spinelli *et al.*, 1983). The different processing methods used in this study reduced phytate from 0.092% for the raw meal to 0.074% for solvent extracted meal, 0.065% for the soaked meal, 0.052% for the boiled meal, 0.043% for mechanically extracted meal and 0.035% for the roasted meal being the least. This is in line with the reports of Iyayi and Egharevba (1998) and Falaye *et al.* (2014) who recorded reduction in phytate content of processed *Mucuna utilis* seeds and lima bean meal respectively. It also agrees with the report of Hossain and Jauncey, (1990) cited in Adesina (2014) which stated that heat treatment reduced the phytic acid content of linseed and sesame meals by up to 72% and 74% respectively.

Conclusion

This study has revealed that roasting proved to be a superior processing method for almond kernel meal based on its ability to reduce the anti-nutritional factors present in the meal and its ability to retain the nutritional value of the meal. This was followed by solvent extraction and mechanical extraction. Roasted almond kernel meal, solvent extracted almond kernel meal and mechanically extracted almond kernel meal had considerable levels of protein and very low levels of anti-nutritional factors, they therefore have high potential of being utilized as low cost unconventional protein concentrates in fish feed. Further studies should be carried out on the bio-availability of almond kernel meals' nutrients to fish.

References

Adesina, S. A. (2014): Nutrient utilization and Growth of Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* Burchell) fed graded levels of differently processed sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* Linnaeus) seed meal. Ph.D Thesis. University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria. 306 p.

Annongu, A.A., Ogundun N.J., Joseph K.J. and Awopetu V. (2006): Changes in chemical composition and bioassay assessment of nutritional potentials of almond fruit waste as an alternative feedstuff for livestock. *Biokemistry*, 18,1, 25-30.

AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemist) (2005): Official methods of analysis (18th Ed.). Washington, D.C., U.S.A.

Balogun, B. I. (2013): Effect of Processing Methods on Anti-Nutritional Levels of *Bauhinia monandra* Kurz. Seed. *PAT* 9(2): 88-101. Accessed from www.patnsukjournal.net/currentissue on 20th October, 2014.

Bello, O. S., Olaifa, F. E. and Emikpe, B. O. (2012): The effect of walnut (*Tetracarpidium conophorum*) leaf and onion (*Allium cepa*) bulb residues on growth performance and nutrient utilization of *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 4,12, 205-213.

Burkill, H. M. (1988): The useful plant of West Tropical Africa. *Royal Botanical Garden. Review*, 1, 418-419.

Duncan, D.B. (1955): Multiple F-test. *Biometrics*, 11, 1-42.

Elezuo, K. O., Akalonu, M. N. and Eboigbe, J. J. (2011): Evaluation of the nutrient composition of some unconventional feedstuffs. *Continental Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science*, 5, 2, 1-5.

Ezeokonkwo, C.A; Dodson W. L. (2004): The Potential of *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical almond) seed as a source of dietary protein. *J. Food Qual.*, 27, 3, 207 – 219.

Fagbenro, O. A., Adeparusi, E. O., and Jimoh, W. A. (2010): Nutritional evaluation of sunflower and sesame seed meals in *Clarias gariepinus*: An assessment by growth performance and nutrient utilization. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 5, 22, 3096-3101.

Falaye, A. E. Adesina, S. A. and Olusola, S. E. (2016): Growth Response and Nutrient utilization of *Clarias gariepinus* Juveniles Fed Differently Processed Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* Linnaeus) Seed Meal-Based Diets. *American Journal of Experimental Agriculture*, 10, 1, 1-11

Falaye, A. E., Omoike, A. and Orisasona, O. (2014): Apparent digestibility Coefficient of Differently Processed Lima Bean (*Phaseolus lunatus* L.) for *Clarias gariepinus* juveniles. *Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science*. 10 pp.

Giami, S. Y. and Ikpimi, I. (1992): The effects of soaking and cooking of winged bean (*Psophocarpus tetragonolobus* LDC). *Nigerian Journal of Nutrition Science*, 13, 45-49.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Griffiths, D. W. (1991): Condensed tannins. In: D'Mello, F.J.P., Duffus, C.M. and Duffus, J. H. (Eds.). Toxic substances in Crop Plants. The Royal Society of Chemistry, Thomas Graham House, Science Park, Cambridge CB4 4WF, Cambridge, pp. 180-201.

Igile, G. O. (1996): Phytochemical and biological studies on some constituents of *Vernonia amygdalina* (compositae) leaves. Ph. D thesis, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Ijeh, I. I. and Elezuo, E. O. (2008): Changes in Malonaldehyde Content of Some Roasted Legumes. *Nigerian J. of Biochem and Molecular Bio.*, 23, 1, 39-41

Iyayi, E. A. and Egharevba, J. I. (1998): Biochemical evaluation of seeds of an under utilized legume (*Mucuna utilis*). *Nigerian Journal of Animal Production*, 25, 1, 40-45.

Johnson, L.A., Suleiman, T.M. and Lusas, E.W. (1979): Sesame protein: a review and prospects. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 56, 463-68.

Kakade, M.L., Hoffa, D.E. and Liener I.E. (1974): Contributions of trypsin inhibitors to the deleterious effects of unheated soybean fed to rats. *J. Nutr.*, 13, 1772-1779

Kersten, G. F., Spiekstra A., Beuvery E. C. and Crommelin D. J. (1991): The structure of immune-stimulating saponin-lipid complexes (iscoms). *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*, 1060, 2, 165-171.

Maga, J.A. (1983): Phytate: Its chemistry: Occurrence, food Interaction, Nutritional significance and Method of Analysis. 122 pp

Molody R. (2008): Almonds and good health. Mineral-rich almond nuts good for bone and cardiovascular health. <http://www.suite101.com/content/almonds-and-good-health-a49468>. November, 2010

New, M. B. and Wijkstrom (2002): Marine ingredients: challenges to their use in aquafeeds. Aqua challenge: Workshop devoted to Aquaculture Challenges in Asia in response to the Bangkok Declaration on Sustainable Aquaculture, Beijing, April 27-30, 2002.

- Nwanna, L. C. (2003): Nutritional Value and Digestibility of Fermented Shrimp Head Waste Meal by African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus*. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 2, 6, 339-345.
- Oakenfull, D. and Sidhu, G. S. (1989): Saponins In Toxicants of plant origin. Vol. II, P. R. Cheeke (Ed.), CRC Press Inc. Florida. Pp 97
- Olapade, O. J. and Kargbo, M. (2012): Growth and hematological responses of the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* Burchell 1882) juveniles to varying inclusions of *Terminalia catappa* (African almond) seed meal based-diets. Proceedings of the 27th Annual Conference and Biennial General meeting of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria held at Banquet Hall Government House/Faculty of Law, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. 25th-30th November, 2012. Pp. 67-70.
- Olukunle, O. A. (1996): Nutritional potential of processed *Sesame indicum* in the diets of *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell 1822) Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Omitoyin, B.O. (1995): Utilization of poultry by-products (feather and offal) in the diets of African Catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell). Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. 249 p.
- Onuoha, P. C. and Elezuo, K. O. (2013): *Basic Principles of Pond Management*. Alego Aries Printer and Publisher, Lagos. 83 pp
- Orisasona, O. (2014): Nutrient utilization and growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* fed graded levels of Lima bean (*Phaseolus lunatus*) meal supplemented with phytase. Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria. 159 p
- Oyelese, O. A. (1994): Nutrient utilization and blood metabolites of *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell) fed varying levels of processed cassava peels. Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. 252 p.
- Rumsey, G. L. (1993): Fishmeal and alternative source of protein in fish feed. *Aquaculture*. 18 No: 7. Pp 14-19.
- Soetan, K. O. (2008): Pharmacological and other beneficial effects of anti-nutritional factors in plants-A review. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.*, 7, 25, 4713-4721.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Solomon, S. G. and Sadiku, S. O. E. (2005): Proximate composition of silkworm caterpillar meal (SCM) (*Anapheinfracta*) processed under thermally controlled and uncontrolled conditions. Proceedings of the 20th annual conference of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria (FISON). Port Harcourt. 14th-18th November, 2005. Pp140-143.

Sotolu, A. O. (2008): Growth performance and nutrient utilization of *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) fed *Leucaena leucocephala* (Lam. de Wit) seed meal-based diets. Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria. 154 p

Spinelli, J., Houle, C. R. and Wekell, J. C. (1983): The effect of phytates on the growth of rainbow trout (*Salmo gairdneri*) fed purified diets containing varying quantities of calcium and magnesium. *Aquaculture*, 30, 71-83.

Sugano, M., Goto, S., Yaoshida, K., Hashimoto, Y., Matsno, T. and Kimoto, M. (1993): Cholesterol-lowering activity of various undigested fractions of soybean protein in rats. *J. Nutr.*, 120, 9, 977-985.

Swain, T. (1979): Tannis and Lignins. In: Rosenthal, G.A and Jansen, D.H. (eds.)

Tacon, A. G. J. (1994): Dependence of intensive aquaculture system on fishmeal and other fishery resources. *FAO Aquaculture Newsletter*, 6, 10-16.

Traditional Tree (2006): Species profiles for Pacific Island Agroforestry. Retrieved from [http//www.traditionaltree.org](http://www.traditionaltree.org). Accessed on 14th March, 2012

Zenk, H. M. (1991): Chasing the enzymes of secondary metabolism: Plant cell cultures as a pot of goal. *Phytochemistry*, 30, 12, 3861-3863.